

Six new species and one new country record of ants of the myrmicine genus *Vombisidris* Bolton, 1991 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from the Philippines, with a new global key to species

DAVID EMMANUEL M. GENERAL^{1,3} AND PERRY ARCHIVAL C. BUENAVENTE²

¹ Research Associate Fellow, National Museum of the Philippines, T.M. Kalaw St., Malate, Manila 1000, Philippines

² Museum Researcher, National Museum of the Philippines, T.M. Kalaw St., Malate, Manila 1000, Philippines

³ Corresponding author: dmgeneral@up.edu.ph

Abstract

Six new species of the myrmicine ant genus *Vombisidris* Bolton, 1991 are described from the Philippines: *deniseae* sp. n. from Kidapawan, Northern Cotabato Province, Mindanao Island; *mangautol* sp. n. from Malaybalay, Bukidnon Province, Mindanao Island; *leonardcoi* sp. n. and *thompsoni* sp. n. from Palanan, Isabela Province, Luzon Island; *sabineschoppea* sp. n., and *starri* sp. n. from Roxas, Palawan Island. In addition, *Vombisidris harpeza* Bolton, 1991 is newly recorded, also from Roxas, Palawan Island. Collection data for five of these species' records (*harpeza*, *leonardcoi* sp. n., *sabineschoppea* sp. n., *starri* sp. n., and *thompsoni* sp. n.) together with observations of *freya* General, 2020, suggest that *Vombisidris* are nocturnal arboreal ants. Thus, it seems possible to find more species of this currently rare genus by simply sampling for them at night. A new global key the 26 species of *Vombisidris*, based on the worker caste, is presented.

Key words: arboreal ant, low vegetation beating, nocturnal sampling, holotype, taxonomy

Introduction

The myrmicine genus *Vombisidris* Bolton, 1991 includes ants with a unique mandibular dentition composed of a large apical tooth followed by two smaller teeth, then a wide diastema, and finally two additional small basal teeth. The width of the diastema is at least as wide as the apical group of teeth. This mandibular dentition is autapomorphic in the subfamily and diagnostic of the genus (Bolton 1991). In addition, most species of *Vombisidris*, with the exception of *V. bilongrudi* (Taylor, 1989), possess on the side of the head a subocular groove that runs from the mandibular attachment to the lateral margin of the occiput.

Since the publication of Bolton (1991), newly discovered species have been described singly and sporadically, in chronological order: *humboldticola* Zacharias and Rajan 2004; *umbrabdomina* Huang and Zhou 2006; *philippina* Zettel and Sorger 2010; *tibeta* Xu and Yu 2012; *freya* General 2020; *satunensis* Jeenthong, Jaitrong, and Tasen 2023; and *sirindhornae* Jeenthong, Samung and Jaitrong, 2025.

All species are known from the worker caste. The dealate queen has been described for only six species: *australis* (Wheeler, 1934); *bilongrudi* (Taylor, 1989); *humboldticola* Zacharias and Rajan, 2004; *renateae* Zacharias and Rajan, 2004; *satunensis* Jeenthong, Jaitrong, and Tasen, 2023; and *sirindhornae* Jeenthong, Samung and Jaitrong, 2025. The male caste is unknown.

Vombisidris ants are predominantly arboreal or semi-arboreal and, partly because of this, their biology remains poorly understood. These ants are rare, with most species known only from the type series consisting of one or a few individuals. The species are also allopatric and widely separated within the genus' distribution range, which extends through from India through Papua New Guinea to Australia.

The diversity of ants in the Philippines remains poorly known. Intensive faunal surveys, incorporating quantitative collecting methods along transects, are only occasionally conducted because of a lack of funding and interested researchers, the difficulty of obtaining collecting permits, and safety concerns in unexplored hinterlands. Each successful survey, without exception, yields new species or new species distribution records. It is necessary to reduce the number of undescribed or "undetermined" species in collections to make the Philippine ant faunal list more meaningful and comprehensive.

This contribution presents the descriptions of six new species from different localities in the Philippines and reports the first extralimital distribution record of a described species, thereby adding to the Philippine *Vombisidris* species list. Figure 1 shows the approximate geographical distribution of Philippine *Vombisidris* species based on type localities or first collection records. A new global key to the 26 species of *Vombisidris*, based on the worker caste, is also provided.

Materials and Methods

The morphological observations and measurements were made using Nikon SMZ800N equipped with an ocular micrometer. A Sony Exmor CMOS Sensor camera captured digital images that were processed with ToupLite for macOS ver.2.1 and stacked with Focus Stacker.

The following measurements, in mm, and indices were taken and computed:

HL - Head Length, in full-face view, maximum distance between the midpoint of an imaginary transverse line drawn between posterior lobes of head, if present, and anteriormost point of clypeus

HW - Head Width, in full-face view, maximum width measured behind the eye

SL - Scape Length, length of scape not including the condyle and neck of scape

EL - Eye Length, maximum width of eye along longest axis

WL - Weber's Length, in lateral view, the diagonal length of the mesosoma between the point where pronotum meets the cervical shield and posterior angle of propodeal lobe

PW - Pronotal Width, in dorsal view, the maximum width of the pronotum

FL - Hind Femur Length, in anterior view, maximum length of hind femur

CI - Cephalic Index: $HW/HL \times 100$

SI - Scape Index: $SL/HW \times 100$

EI - Eye Index: $EL/HW \times 100$

FI - Hind Femur Index: $FL/HW \times 100$

Permits

The specimens studied in this contribution were collected under the collecting permits for the following localities:

1. UP Dynamic Plot, Barangay (=Village) Villarobles, Palanan, Isabela Province, Luzon Island – GP# 2024-02 issued by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) to Mr. Earl Terrenz Gigante, M.S. student at the University of the Philippines.
2. Barangay Dumarao, Roxas, Palawan Province - GP #2018-05 (R2) issued by the Palawan Council for Sustainable Development Staff (PCSDS) to Dr. Sabine Schoppe of Katala Foundation, Inc.
3. Barangay St. Peter, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon Province - GP #2018-01 issued by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) to Dr. Victor Amoroso of Central Mindanao University.
4. Energy Development Corporation (EDC), Kidapawan, North Cotabato Province, Mindanao Island - RCCMD-A-CT-2024-24 issued by the National Museum of the Philippines (PNM), pursuant to Republic Act Nos. 10066 and 11333, to Rolly Urriza of PNM.

Depositories

MCZC - Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA

PCSDS - Palawan Council for Sustainable Development Staff, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan Province, Philippines

PNM - National Museum of Natural History, National Museum of the Philippines, Manila, Philippines

UPLB - Entomological Collection, Museum of Natural History, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Los Baños, Laguna Province, Philippines

Figure 1. Approximate geographic distribution of *Vombisidris* species in the Philippines, based on the type locality or first record of collection.

Taxonomy

Class Insecta Linnaeus, 1858

Order Hymenoptera Linnaeus, 1858

Family Formicidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Myrmicinae Lepeletier de Saint-Fargeau, 1835

Genus *Vombisidris* Bolton, 1991

Checklist of species of *Vombisidris*

Species

acherdos Bolton, 1991

australis (Wheeler, 1934)

bilongrudi (Taylor, 1989)

***deniseae* sp. n.**

dryas Bolton, 1991

freyae General, 2020

harpeza Bolton, 1991

humboldticola Zacharias and Rajan, 2004

jacobsoni (Forel, 1915)

Country of Distribution

Papua New Guinea

Australia

Papua New Guinea

Philippines

Malaysia

Philippines

Malaysia, Philippines (new)

India

Indonesia

<i>leonardcoi</i> sp. n.	Philippines
<i>lochme</i> Bolton, 1991	Indonesia
<i>mangautol</i> sp. n.	Philippines
<i>nahet</i> Bolton, 1991	Indonesia
<i>occidua</i> Bolton, 1991	India
<i>philax</i> Bolton, 1991	Indonesia
<i>philippina</i> Zettel and Sorger, 2010	Philippines
<i>regina</i> Bolton, 1991	Malaysia
<i>renateae</i> (Taylor, 1989)	Australia
<i>sabineschoppea</i> sp. n.	Philippines
<i>satunensis</i> Jeenthong, Jaitrong, and Tasen, 2023	Thailand
<i>sirindhornae</i> Jeenthong, Samung and Jaitrong, 2025	Thailand
<i>starri</i> sp. n.	Philippines
<i>thompsoni</i> sp. n.	Philippines
<i>tibeta</i> Xu and Yu, 2012	China
<i>umbrabdomina</i> Huang and Zhou, 2006	China
<i>xylochos</i> Bolton, 1991	Brunei Darussalam

Species Accounts

Vombisidris deniseae sp. n. (Figs. 2-5)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:8F237477-2B9F-4BB4-992A-96D27D0485B4

Diagnosis: A member of the *philax* species group, this species possesses a tooth on either side of the dorsolateral mesosoma, a character shared only with *V. philax* Bolton, 1991. However, *V. deniseae* sp. n. possesses an impressed metanotal groove and a smooth first gastral tergite.

Holotype measurements (in mm) (paratype measurements in parentheses): HL 0.76 (0.76), HW ,0.66 (0.65), SL 0.50 (0.50), EL 0.20 (0.19), WL 1.04 (1.00), PW 0.55 (0.51), FL 0.65 (0.63), CI 87 (85), SI 75 (77), EI 30 (29), FI 98 (96).

Material examined: Holotype, PHILIPPINES, Mindanao Island, North Cotabato Province, Kidapawan, EDC Site B, ex. diurnal beating, 27.vii.2024, leg. P.A.C. Buenavente (PNM18884); Paratype (n=1) same data (MCZC).

Description

Structures: Head subrectangular, with lateral margins subparallel, sides behind eyes subparallel; dorsum rugoreticulate, interspaces shallowly punctulate. Posterior margin of head shallowly emarginate medially. Torulus covered by short, narrow frontal lobes. Antennal scrobes indistinct, only traceable by slightly more prominent sculpture just behind torulus that forms the dorsal edge of scrobe. Subocular groove complete, meeting occipital margin. Clypeus strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin covered by this convexity. Eyes weakly convex, comparatively large, containing 9-10 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles smooth, with distinct hair pits. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar peduncle, petiolar node, and postpetiole with well-developed rugoreticulum. In lateral view, dorsum of mesosoma weakly convex; promesonotal suture absent; small tooth present just below the dorsolateral margin, behind the position of the promesonotal suture; metanotal groove weakly impressed; propodeal dorsum almost flat; propodeal spines set at high position, short, just extending beyond posterior edge of propodeal lobe, subparallel in dorsal view. Petiole with short indistinct peduncle bearing pair of short teeth in front of spiracle; petiolar node indistinct in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle approximately at (slightly in front of) midlength of peduncle. Postpetiole in dorsal

view subtrapezoidal, widest anteriorly. Gaster slightly depressed; dorsum smooth, except short striae laterally at base of tergite 1.

Pilosity: Dorsum of head with abundant, short, sharp erect setae; leading edge of scape with alternating long, sharp, erect setae and short, sharp, decumbent setae; dorsum of mesosoma with abundant erect sharp setae, distinctly longer than on head; sparse erect sharp setae on dorsum of petiole, postpetiole, and gaster, slightly shorter than those of mesosoma.

Color: head, mandibles, antennae, mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster concolourously yellow. Legs lighter yellow.

Etymology. This species is lovingly named for my second daughter, Denise Marie G. Booth, who also happens to be the mother of Freya (see General 2020).

Comparative Notes

Only *V. philax* and *V. deniseae* **sp. n.** possess a tooth on the dorsolateral margin of the mesosoma. *Vombisidris deniseae* **sp. n.** differs from *V. philax* in possessing less prominent eyes (in full-face view), an impressed metanotal groove, a much shorter propodeal spine, a shorter petiolar peduncle, and a dorsally truncate petiolar node (all in lateral view), as well as a smooth first gastral tergite.

Figures 2-5. *Vombisidris deniseae* **sp. n.** Holotype. (2) Frontal head view. (3) Lateral view. (4) Dorsal view. (5) Labels.

Vombisidris leonardcoi **sp. n.** (Figs. 6-9)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:CF3FC98A-5126-4BEB-85A2-37C944C3BF91

Diagnosis: A member of the *dryas* species group, this species possesses, in full-face view, a feebly diverging lateral margin of head behind the eyes, and in lateral view, a weakly impressed metanotal groove, short propodeal spines, a differentiated petiolar node, and abundant short blunt erect setae on the head and gaster but sparse on the mesosoma.

Holotype measurements (in mm) (mean and range in parentheses, n=6): HL 0.78 (0.74; 0.70-0.78), HW 0.70 (0.66; 0.63-0.70), SL 0.50 (0.49; 0.45-0.50), EL 0.19 (0.18; 0.16-0.19), WL 1.00 (0.96; 0.91-1.00),

PW 0.54 (0.51; 0.50-0.54), FL 0.59 (0.57; 0.53-0.59), CI 90 (89; 87-91), SI 71 (71-77), EI 27 (27; 25-29), FI 84 (87; 84-90)

Material examined: Holotype, PHILIPPINES, Luzon Island, Isabela Province, Palanan, Barangay [=Village] Villarobles, UP Dynamic Plot, nocturnal beating, ex transect study, 20.vi-10.vii.2024, leg. T. Gigante et al. (PNM18885); Paratypes (n=5), same data.

Figures 6-9. *Vombisidris leonardcoi* sp. n. Holotype. (6) Frontal head view. (7) Lateral view. (8) Dorsal view. (9) Labels.

Structures: Head longer than wide, with lateral margins converging anteriorly, sides behind eyes feebly divergent; dorsum with distinct rugoreticulum, interspaces mostly smooth. Torulus covered by short, narrow frontal lobes. Posterior margin of head medially shallowly emarginate. Antennal scrobes indistinct, only traceable by slightly more prominent sculpture just behind torulus that forms the dorsal edge of scrobe. Subocular groove complete, meeting occipital margin. Clypeus strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin covered by this convexity. Eyes strongly protruding, comparatively large, containing 9-10 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles smooth, without distinct hair pits. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole with distinct coarse rugoreticulum; dorsum of petiolar peduncle with very finely reticulate sculpture. In lateral view dorsum of mesosoma very weakly curved; metanotal groove impressed; propodeal dorsum gently downcurved; propodeal spines set at high position, short, never reaching node of petiole in outstretched specimen, distinctly curved in dorsal view. Petiole with long peduncle bearing pair of short teeth in front of spiracle; anterior and dorsal face of node forming a blunt angle in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle approximately at (slightly in front of) midlength of peduncle. Postpetiole in dorsal view roughly pentagonal, widest anteriorly. Gaster slightly depressed; dorsum smooth, except short striae at base of tergite 1.

Pilosity: head with abundant, short blunt erect setae, leading edge of antennal scape with a row of eight sharp, erect setae, as long as width of scape; dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole with sparse, relatively long, blunt erect setae (distinctly longer than those on head); gaster with standing setae hardly shorter than those of mesosoma.

Color: head, mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster almost uniformly brown. Mandibles, antennae, and legs yellowish brown.

Bionomics. This species was collected by nocturnal beating of low vegetation in a transect study in primary forest.

Etymology. This species is named in honor of the late Prof. Leonard Co, botanist extraordinaire, who established the University of the Philippines Dynamic Plot in Palanan, Isabela Province and was an indefatigable advocate of environmental protection. He was tragically shot and killed in the field by the authorities in a mis-encounter.

Comparative Notes

This species fails at couplet 6 in the key of Jeenthong et al. (2023). It is similar to *V. tibeta* in possessing a medially emarginate posterior margin of the head except that its propodeal spiracle is situated higher and more forward and the petiole node is clearly differentiated.

***Vombisidris mangautol* sp. n.** (Figs. 10-13)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:334AF4F9-6C19-4450-AD9F-66B87CB002F7

Diagnosis: A member of the *dryas* species group, this species possesses a combination of an undifferentiated petiole node, metanotal groove impressed, posterior margin of head entire, propodeal spine short, curved in lateral view but subparallel in dorsal view, sharp erect setae abundant and short on head but sparse and long on mesosoma and gaster. Body color orange with lighter legs.

Holotype measurements (in mm): HL 0.81, HW 0.71, SL 0.63, EL 0.20, WL 1.19, PW 0.59, FL 0.63, CI 88, SI 88, EI 28, FI 88.

Material examined: Holotype, PHILIPPINES, Mindanao Island, Bukidnon Province, Malaybalay City, Barangay [=Village] St. Peter, Pantaron Range, Mt. Bungkasan, 1060 masl, diurnal beating, ex transect study, 11-17.x.2019, leg. D.E.M. General (PNM18879).

Structures: Head longer than broad, with lateral margins subparallel, sides behind eyes slightly convergent; dorsum rugoreticulate, interspaces mostly smooth. Torulus obscured by short, narrow frontal lobes. Posterior margin of head entire. Antennal scrobes indistinct, indicated only by slight depression in oblique lateral view. Subocular groove complete, reaching occipital margin. Clypeus opaque, strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin obscured by this convexity. Eyes convex, comparatively large, containing 10-11 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles faintly longitudinally striate, with distinct piliferous punctulae. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole coarsely rugoreticulate; dorsum of petiolar peduncle opaque, finely reticulate. In lateral view, dorsum of mesosoma scarcely curved; metanotal groove shallow; propodeal dorsum continuing the weak curvature of the mesosoma; propodeal spines located at top of propodeal declivity, short, never reaching node of petiole in outstretched specimen, distinctly curved in dorsal view. Petiole with short peduncle, unarmed laterally; anterior face of node almost indistinguishable from peduncle; dorsal face of node forming a blunt angle with posterior face in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle well in front of midlength of peduncle. In dorsal view, postpetiole subtrapezoidal, widest anteriorly. Gaster dorsum smooth, except short striae at base of tergite 1.

Pilosity; on head, sharp erect setae near occipital region slightly longer than on frons, leading edge of scape with six widely separated long sharp erect setae, about 1.5-2X as long as width of scape, among shorter decumbent setae; erect setae on head dorsum abundant; sparse, sharp, erect setae on mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster distinctly longer than longest setae on head.

Color of entire body orange, legs lighter in color.

Bionomics: This species was collected by diurnal beating of low vegetation in a transect study (General 2021).

Etymology. This species is affectionately named in honor of my siblings (*mga utol* is the plural form of *utol*, colloquial Tagalog term for sibling). The species epithet, Latinized and spelled for ease of pronunciation, is a noun in apposition and invariant.

Comparative Notes

Known only from the holotype, *V. mangautol* keys out to *V. australis* in Jeenthong et al. (2023) but is larger (HW 0.71 vis-a-vis HW 0.63-0.68 in *V. australis* in Taylor (1989)) and more coarsely sculptured, lacks both the broader, angulate mesosoma, in dorsal view, and the distinctively flat petiolar node, in lateral view.

This species was listed as "*Vombisidris* sp. undet1" in General (2021).

Figures 10-13. *Vombisidris mangautol* sp. n. Holotype. (10) Frontal head view. (11) Lateral view. (12) Dorsal view. (13) Labels.

Vombisidris sabineschoppea sp. n. (Figs. 14-17)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:D961FFF3-8470-49DF-960D-99277A4B5FEA

Diagnosis: A member of the *philax* species group, this species possesses a combination of posterior margin of head entire, petiole node differentiated from peduncle by an obtuse angle, metanotal groove absent, propodeal spine long and slightly downcurved, erect setae on dorsal surfaces long, sharp, and abundant. Body color dark brown, appendages yellowish brown.

Holotype measurements (in mm): HL 0.76, HW 0.66, SL 0.55, EL 0.18, WL 1.05, PW 0.56, FL 0.73, CI 87, SI 83, EI 26, FI 109.

Material examined: Holotype, PHILIPPINES, Palawan Island, Palawan Province, Roxas, Barangay [=Village] Dumarao, Lower Ilian- Masaya 1-Maharlika Local Conservation Area, nocturnal beating, ex demonstration transect, 17.viii.2022, leg. Z. Griebenow (PNM18883).

Structures: Head longer than wide, sides behind eyes subparallel; dorsum with distinct rugoreticulum, interspaces punctulate. Torulus obscured by short, narrow frontal lobes. Posterior margin of head entire. Antennal scrobes indistinct, indicated only by slight depression in oblique lateral view. Subocular groove complete, reaching occipital margin. Clypeus strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin obscured by this convexity. Eyes strongly protruding, comparatively large, containing 9-10 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles entirely smooth. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole coarsely rugoreticulate; dorsum of petiolar peduncle shallowly punctulate. In lateral view, dorsum of mesosoma evenly but shallowly convex; metanotal groove absent; propodeal dorsum continuing the curvature of the mesosoma; propodeal spines (left spine broken) located relatively high on propodeum, long, curved in both lateral and dorsal views. Petiole with short peduncle; petiole node low; anterior and dorsal faces of node forming a blunt obtuse angle in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle at about midlength of peduncle; a blunt tooth produced posteriorly. Postpetiole in dorsal view roughly globular, widest anteriorly. Gaster dorsum smooth, except short striae at base of tergite 1.

Pilosity: on dorsum of head, abundant, blunt, erect setae near occipital region longer than on frons, leading edge of scape with a row of 8-10 sharp erect setae about 1-1.5X as long as width of scape; blunt erect setae on mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster sub-equal or longer than longest setae on head.

Color: head, mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster almost uniformly brown, although anterior half of pronotum and apex of gaster yellowish brown (possibly not yet fully infuscated). Appendages yellowish brown.

Bionomics. This species was collected by nocturnal beating of low vegetation in secondary forest.

Figures 14-17. *Vombisidris sabineschoppea* sp. n. Holotype. (14) Frontal head view. (15) Lateral view. (16) Dorsal view. (17) Labels.

Etymology. This species is respectfully named in honor of Dr. Sabine Schoppe, a fierce wildlife conservationist and the driving force of the Katala Foundation, Inc. on Palawan Island, the last bastion of Philippine wildlife.

Comparative Notes

Known only from the holotype, with a short peduncle, *V. sabineschoppea* keys out to *V. harpeza* in Jeenthong et al. (2023), but lacks the distinct petiolar node, is smaller (HW 0.66 to HW 0.75 in *V. harpeza* in Bolton 1991), much darker in color, more coarsely sculptured, and with relatively longer, curved spines. This species may also be mistaken for *V. philippina* but the leg segments are concolorously yellow and the petiole node is not differentiated from the peduncle by an obtuse angle.

***Vombisidris starri* sp. n.** (Figs. 18-21)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:32AEEBCB-0441-49E4-A784-8EDF78C529EF

Diagnosis: A member of the *australis* species group, this species possesses a combination of a petiole node differentiated from peduncle by an obtuse angle, metanotal groove absent, and lateral margins of the head behind the eyes convergent, antennal scrobe prominent, propodeal spines with wide base, long and straight in lateral view, subparallel in dorsal view. Erect setae sharp, abundant on dorsal surfaces of head, mesosoma, and gaster. Erect setae on head shorter than on mesosoma and gaster. Head and mesosoma dark yellow, gaster yellow.

Holotype measurements (in mm): HL 0.94, HW 0.78, SL 0.63, EL 0.21, WL 1.19, PW 0.60, FL 0.78, CI 83, SI 81, EI 27, FI 100.

Material examined: Holotype, PHILIPPINES, Palawan Island, Palawan Province, Roxas, Barangay [=Village] Dumarao, Lower Ilian- Masaya 1-Maharlika Local Conservation Area, nocturnal beating, ex demonstration transect, 17.viii.2022, leg. Z. Lieberman (PNM18882).

Description

Structures: Head longer than wide, sides behind eyes subparallel; dorsum with distinct rugoreticulum, interspaces punctulate. Torulus obscured by short, narrow frontal lobes. Posterior margin of head shallowly emarginate medially. Antennal scrobes distinct. Subocular groove complete, reaching occipital margin. Clypeus strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin obscured by this convexity. Eyes strongly protruding, comparatively large, containing 9-10 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles entirely smooth. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole coarsely rugoreticulate; dorsum of petiolar peduncle shallowly punctulate. In lateral view, dorsum of mesosoma evenly but shallowly convex; metanotal groove absent; propodeal dorsum continuing the curvature of the mesosoma; propodeal spines located relatively low on propodeum, long with a thick base, straight in lateral but subparallel in dorsal view. Petiole with short peduncle; petiole node low; anterior and dorsal faces of node forming a blunt obtuse angle in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle at about midlength of peduncle; a blunt tooth produced posteriorly. Postpetiole in dorsal view roughly trapezoidal, widest anteriorly. Gaster dorsum smooth, except short striae at base of tergite 1.

Pilosity: on dorsum of head, abundant, sharp, erect setae near occipital region longer than on frons, leading edge of scape with a row of 8-10 sharp erect setae about 1-1.5X as long as width of scape; long, sharp erect setae on mesosoma, dorsum of spine, and petiole about 2X as long as longest setae on head.

Color: head, antenna, mandibles, mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, uniformly yellowish brown. Gaster and legs yellow.

Bionomics. This species was collected by nocturnal beating of low vegetation in secondary forest.

Etymology. This species is respectfully named in honor of my friend, Dr. Christopher K. Starr, retired professor of Entomology at the University of Trinidad and Tobago, who introduced me to the study of stinging Hymenoptera when he was a visiting professor here in the Philippines.

Comparative Notes

This species keys out to *V. harpeza* in Jeenthong et al. (2023) but has long sharp erect setae, a prominent antennal scrobe, and propodeal spine supported by a broad base.

In frontal view, the lateral margins of the head behind the eyes are converging, similar to *V. humboldticola* but has a differentiated petiolar node and a wide base of the propodeal spine. With a prominent antennal scrobe, this is similar to *V. satunensis* but has converging lateral margins behind the head, a yellow gaster, and long sharp erect setae.

Figures 18-21. *Vombisidris starri* sp. n. Holotype. (18) Frontal head view. (19) Lateral view. (20) Dorsal view. (21) Labels.

Vombisidris thompsoni sp. n. (Figs. 22-25)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:F79C31C8-90F5-4D1B-B3DE-1D8B256B6745

Diagnosis: A member of the *philax* species group, this species possesses a combination of an undifferentiated petiolar node, absent metanotal groove, narrowly emarginate posterior margin of the head, short straight propodeal spines that are subparallel in dorsal view, abundant erect sharp setae on the dorsal surfaces of the head and mesosoma but sparse on the gaster, erect setae on head shorter than on mesosoma and gaster. Body color yellow.

Holotype measurements (in mm) (mean and range in parentheses, n=3): HL 0.69 (0.68; 0.65-0.70), HW 0.53 (0.55; 0.53-0.56), SL 0.50 (0.51; 0.50-0.53), EL 0.18 (0.18; 0.18-0.19), WL 0.86 (0.89; 0.86-0.94), PW 0.43 (0.43; 0.43-0.44), FL 0.55 (0.57; 0.55-0.59), CI 76 (80; 76-85), SI 95 (93; 91-95), EI 33 (34; 33-34), FI 105 (104; 102-105)

Material examined: Holotype, PHILIPPINES, Luzon Island, Isabela Province, Palanan, Barangay [=Village] Villarobles, UP Dynamic Plot, nocturnal beating, ex transect study, 20.vi-10.vii.2024, leg. T. Gigante et al. (PNM18880); Paratypes (n=2), same data.

Structures: Head slender, with lateral margins subparallel, sides behind eyes subparallel; dorsum with weakly developed rugoreticulum, interspaces mostly smooth. Torulus covered by short, narrow frontal lobes. Posterior margin of head shallowly emarginate medially. Antennal scrobes indistinct, only traceable by slightly more prominent sculpture just behind torulus that forms the dorsal edge of scrobe. Subocular groove complete, meeting occipital margin. Clypeus strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin covered by this convexity. Eyes strongly protruding, comparatively large, containing 9-10 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles smooth, with distinct hair pits. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar peduncle, petiolar node, and postpetiole with weakly developed rugoreticulum. In lateral view, dorsum of mesosoma almost flat; metanotal groove absent; propodeal dorsum almost flat; propodeal spines set at high position, short, just extending beyond posterior edge of propodeal lobe, subparallel in dorsal view. Petiole with long peduncle bearing pair of short teeth in front of spiracle; petiolar node indistinct in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle approximately at (slightly in front of) midlength of peduncle. Postpetiole in dorsal view subtrapezoidal, widest anteriorly. Gaster slightly depressed; dorsum smooth, except short striae at base of tergite 1.

Figures 22-25. *Vombisidris thompsoni* sp. n. Holotype. (22) Frontal head view. (23) Lateral view. (24) Dorsal view. (25) Labels.

Pilosity: Dorsum of head with abundant, short, sharp erect setae; leading edge of scape with alternating long, sharp, erect setae and short, sharp, decumbent setae; dorsum of mesosoma with abundant suberect sharp setae, distinctly longer than on head; a mixture of erect and sub-erect sharp setae on dorsum of petiole, postpetiole, and gaster, slightly longer than those of mesosoma.

Color: head, mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster concolourously yellowish brown. Mandibles, antennae yellow yellowish brown. Coxae, femora, and tibiae lighter.

Bionomics. This species was collected by nocturnal beating of low vegetation in a transect study in primary forest.

Etymology. This species is gratefully named in honor of my masteral major professor, Dr. Lynne C. Thompson, of the then School of Forest Resources of the University of Arkansas at Monticello, who taught me more about life than he realizes.

Comparative Notes

In the global key of Jeenthong et al. (2023), this species fails at couplet 6, sharing a weakly concave posterior margin of head, convex anterior clypeal margin, and a poorly differentiated petiolar node with *V. tibeta*, but is smaller (HL 0.65-0.70 mm) and has straight propodeal spines that are much shorter than the propodeal dorsum.

New Philippine record of species

Vombisidris harpeza Bolton, 1991 (Figs. 26-29)

Diagnosis: A member of the *australis* species group, this species possesses a weakly impressed metanotal groove, petiole node differentiated from the peduncle by an obtuse angle, short blunt erect setae abundant on head and gaster but sparse on mesosoma.

Measurements (in mm) (mean and range in parentheses, n=3): HL (0.73; 0.69-0.75), HW (0.64; 0.63-0.66), SL (0.50; 0.50), EL (0.19; 0.19-0.20), WL (0.95; 0.90-0.98), PW (0.52; 0.50-0.56), FL (0.57; 0.56-0.59), CI (88; 85-91), SI (78; 75-80), EI (38; 38-40), FI (90; 85-94).

Material examined: worker (n=3); PHILIPPINES, Palawan Island, Palawan Province, Roxas, Barangay [=Village] Dumarao, Lower Ilian-Masaya 1-Maharlika Local Conservation Area, nocturnal beating, ex transect study, 17.viii.2022, leg. Z. Griebenow (PNM, PCSDS, UPLB).

Description

Structures: Head slightly longer than wide, with lateral margins converging anteriorly, sides behind eyes feebly divergent; dorsum with distinct rugoreticulum, interspaces sparsely punctulate. Torulus covered by short, narrow frontal lobes. Posterior margin of head entire. Antennal scrobes indistinct, only traceable by slightly more prominent sculpture just behind torulus that forms the dorsal edge of scrobe. Subocular groove complete, meeting occipital margin. Clypeus strongly convex in lateral view, in full face view its anterior margin covered by this convexity. Eyes weakly protruding, comparatively large, containing 8-9 ommatidia in longest row. Mandibles finely striate, without distinct hair pits. Dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole with distinct coarse rugoreticulum; dorsum of petiolar peduncle with very finely reticulate sculpture. In lateral view dorsum of mesosoma very weakly convex; metanotal groove weakly impressed; propodeal dorsum gently down-curved; propodeal spines set at high position, short, never reaching node of petiole in outstretched specimen, distinctly curved in dorsal view. Petiole with short peduncle bearing pair of short teeth in front of spiracle; anterior and dorsal face of node forming a blunt angle in lateral view, ventrally with small tooth anteriorly and shallow concavity below node; spiracle approximately at (slightly in front of) midlength of peduncle. Postpetiole in dorsal view roughly trapezoidal, widest anteriorly. Gaster slightly depressed; dorsum smooth.

Pilosity: head with abundant, short blunt erect setae, leading edge of antennal scape with a row of eight sharp, erect setae, as long as width of scape; dorsum of mesosoma, petiolar node, and postpetiole with sparse, relatively long, blunt erect setae (distinctly longer than those on head); gaster with erect setae hardly shorter than those of mesosoma.

Color: head, mandibles, antennae, and legs light yellow; mesosoma, petiole, postpetiole, and gaster yellowish brown.

Bionomics. This species was collected by nocturnal beating of low vegetation in secondary forest.

Comparative Notes

In Bolton (1991) and Jeenthong et al. (2023), these ants keys out to *V. harpeza* but, in the Palawan specimens, the dorsal face of the petiole node is convex and the erect setae on the mesosoma are sparse. The Palawan specimens also have slightly longer scapes (SI 75-80) and have a less conspicuous obtuse angle differentiating the petiole node from the peduncle. These differences are interpreted as geographical variation of the species, considering the wide separation between the Malaysian (Sarawak) and Philippine (Palawan) populations.

Figures 26-29. *Vombisidris harpeza* Bolton, 1991. Nontype. (26) Frontal head view. (27) Lateral view. (28) Dorsal view. (29) Labels.

New global key to the species of *Vombisidris*

(modified from Bolton 1991, Xu and Yu 2012, Jeenthong et al. 2023, and Jeenthong et al. 2025)

- 1 Subocular groove absent (Papua New Guinea).....*bilongrudi* (Taylor, 1989)
- 1' Subocular groove present.....2
- 2(1) Subocular groove incomplete, running only from mandibular insertion to under compound eye (Papua New Guinea).....*acherdos* Bolton, 1991
- 2' Subocular groove complete, running from mandibular insertion to occipital carina.....3
- 3(2) In lateral view, mesonotum dorsally or dorsolaterally armed with a sharp tooth.....4
- 3' In lateral view, mesonotum dorsally unarmed or at most with blunt prominences.....5

- 4(3) Anterior 2/3 of first gastral tergite rugulose; metanotal groove absent (Indonesia: Sulawesi)*philax* Bolton, 1991
- 4' First gastral tergite entirely smooth; metanotal groove impressed (Philippines: Mindanao Island)*deniseae* n.sp.
- 5(3) In lateral view, petiolar node clearly differentiated from peduncle by an obtuse angle.....6
- 5' In lateral view, petiolar node poorly differentiated from peduncle, with its dorsal margin smoothly rising posteriorly to apex of node.....15
- 6(5) In lateral view, metanotal groove absent, so that the dorsal outline is a continuous curve.....7
- 6' In lateral view, metanotal groove present, so that the dorsal outline is interrupted by a shallow or deep furrow at the juncture between the promesonotum and the propodeum.....10
- 7(6) Head and mesosoma brown (Philippines: Palawan Island).....*sabineschoppea* n. sp.
- 7' Head and mesosoma yellow or yellowish brown.....8
- 8(7) In frontal view, lateral margins of head behind the eyes converging posteriorly (Philippines: Palawan Island).....*starri* n. sp.
- 8' In frontal view, lateral margins of head behind the eyes subparallel.....9
- 9(8) In lateral view, propodeal spines long and slender with narrow bases; erect setae on gaster long and blunt (Australia: Queensland).....*renateae* (Taylor, 1989)
- 9' In lateral view, propodeal spines long and robust with thick bases; erect setae on gaster short and sharp (Thailand: Kamphaeng Phet Province).....*sirindhornae* Jeenthong, Samung, and Jaitrong, 2025
- 10(6) In lateral view, metanotal groove shallow or indistinct.....11
- 10' In lateral view, metanotal groove distinctly impressed.....12
- 11(10) In lateral view, petiole node truncate dorsally, with a flat dorsal surface between sharp anterior and posterior angles; in dorsal view, propodeal spines divergent; body color brown (Australia: Queensland).....*australis* (Wheeler, 1934)
- 11' In lateral view, petiole node slightly rounded dorsally, without sharp angles anteriorly or posteriorly; in dorsal view, propodeal spines curved inward; body color yellow (Malaysia: Sarawak).....*harpeza* Bolton, 1991
- 12(10) In lateral view, propodeal spine longer than propodeal dorsum; pronotum almost flat (Brunei Darussalam).....*xylochos* Bolton, 1991
- 12' In lateral view, propodeal spine shorter than propodeal dorsum; pronotum convex.....13
- 13(12) In frontal view, lateral margin of head behind eyes subparallel (Malaysia: Sarawak).....*dryas* Bolton, 1991
- 13' In frontal view, lateral margin of head behind eyes diverging posteriorly.....14
- 14(13) In lateral view, propodeal spine straight; erect setae on mesosoma abundant (Indonesia: Sulawesi)*lochme* Bolton, 1991
- 14' In lateral view, propodeal spine slightly downcurved distally; erect setae on mesosoma sparse (Philippines: Luzon Island).....*leonardcoi* n.sp.

- 15(5) In lateral view, metanotal groove deeply impressed.....**16**
 15' In lateral view, metanotal groove shallow or absent.....**20**
- 16(15) In frontal view, anterior clypeal margin broadly and deeply emarginate; compound eyes prominently dome-like (Malaysia: Sabah).....*regina* Bolton, 1991
 16' In frontal view, anterior clypeal margin entire or convex; compound eyes convex but not prominently dome-like.....**17**
- 17(16) In frontal view, anterior clypeal margin produced into a rounded angle; erect setae on dorsum of head sparse (China: Tibet).....*tibeta* Xu and Yu, 2012
 17' In frontal view, anterior clypeal margin convex, but not produced into a rounded angle; erect setae on dorsum of head abundant.....**18**
- 18(17) In frontal view, posterior margin of head shallowly emarginate; head and body concolorously brown (Indonesia: Sumatra).....*jacobsoni* (Forel, 1915)
 18' In frontal view, posterior margin of head entire; head and body yellow or yellowish brown.....**19**
- 19(18) In frontal view, lateral margin of head behind eyes converging posteriorly; erect setae on dorsum of mesosoma and gaster abundant; gaster darker in color than head and mesosoma (China: Hunan)*umbrabdomina* Huang and Zhou, 2006
 19' In frontal view, lateral margin of head behind eyes subparallel; erect setae on dorsum of mesosoma and gaster sparse; gaster same color as head and mesosoma (Philippines: Mindanao Island).....*mangautol* n. sp.
- 20(15) Tibiae white, in sharp contrast to color of other leg segments (Philippines: Cebu Island)*philippina* Zettel and Sorger, 2010
 20' Tibiae of same color as other leg segments.....**21**
- 21(20) In frontal view, lateral margin of head behind eyes converging posteriorly.....**22**
 21' In frontal view, lateral margin of head behind eyes subparallel.....**23**
- 22(21) Gaster lighter in color than head and mesosoma (Indonesia: Sulawesi).....*nahet* Bolton, 1991
 22' Gaster darker in color than head and mesosoma (India: Kerala).....*humboldticola* Zacharias and Rajan, 2004
- 23(21) In dorsal view, propodeal spines divergent; head and mesosoma dark brown (India).....*occidua* Bolton, 1991
 23' In dorsal view, propodeal spines subparallel or curved inward, never divergent **24**
- 24(23) Gaster brown, darker in color than yellowish brown head and mesosoma (Thailand: Satun Province).....*satunensis* Jeenthong, Jaitrong, and Tasen 2023
 24' Gaster yellow, concolorous with head and mesosoma.....**25**
- 25(24) In dorsal view, propodeal spines curved; erect setae on dorsal surface of head, short and blunt; on mesosoma, and gaster long and blunt; erect setae on gaster abundant (Philippines: Luzon Island)*freyae* General, 2020
 25' In dorsal view, propodeal spines subparallel; erect setae on dorsal surface of head, short and sharp; on mesosoma, and gaster long and sharp; erect setae on gaster sparse (Philippines: Luzon Island)*thompsoni* n. sp.

Discussion

Arboreal ants are rather challenging to survey without appropriate techniques and equipment. For the collection of *Vombisidris* ants, beating of low vegetation has proven to be sufficiently effective. Interestingly, nocturnal beating revealed an unexpected and astonishingly distinct community of nocturnal arboreal ants, which included a previously undescribed species of *Vombisidris* (General et al. 2020).

During a demonstration of transect collecting techniques on Palawan Island in 2022, three species: *sabineschoppea* sp. n., *starri* sp. n., and *harpeza*, were collected from a transect comprising only three adjoining 5-m radius plots with a total area of only ~236 m². This degree of sympatry within the genus is unprecedented. Subsequently, in the 2024 Palanan, Isabela transect study composed of ten adjacent 5-m radius plots, two new species: *leonardcoi* sp. n. and *thompsoni* sp. n. were collected. The discovery of these new species in close proximity challenges previous perceptions of *Vombisidris* as being strictly allopatric in distribution.

Vombisidris ants are rarely collected, and even the material treated in this contribution comprises very few individuals per species. Bolton (1991) described five species based on singletons: *dryas*, *harpeza*, *lochme*, *occidua*, and *xylochos*. Likewise, Huang and Zhou (2006) described *umbrabdomina* from a single specimen. In the present study, the following species are likewise described from unique specimens: *mangautol* sp. n., *sabineschoppea* sp. n., and *starri* sp. n. Although describing species based on singletons is not ideal, it is preferable to leaving specimens indefinitely labeled as “sp. 1”, “sp. 2”, and so forth.

The discovery of two or even three species within the same transect suggests that additional new species may be detected through both diurnal and, especially, nocturnal sampling of arboreal ants. It is possible that *Vombisidris* “sp. A” of Zettel and Sorger (2010) may eventually be matched with worker material.

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